

CLASSIFICATION OF IRONY AND FEATURES OF EACH TYPE

Ramazonova Farangiz Mukhiddin qizi ¹, Arustamyan Y. Y. ²

¹The National University named after Mirzo Ulugbek Department of theory of translation and comparative linguistics

²Scientific adviser: DSc., Assoc. prof.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4887830>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th May 2021

Accepted: 25th May 2021

Online: 30th May 2021

KEY WORDS

classification, types of irony, figurative meanings, sarcasm.

ABSTRACT

This article deals with analyses and the notion of irony, classification of types of irony from the point of view of different Russian researchers. In a wider sense irony is a literary technique, rhetorical device, or event in which what appears on the facial to be the case or to be awaited contradicts totally the reality. Irony can occur in both tragic and humorous situations.

The term irony is used when people express their thoughts or ideas in a certain situation by using language that normally has the opposite meaning, typically for humorous or emphatic effect.

There are many classifications of types of irony. Species are distinguished according to different characteristics. Since the object itself is infinitely diverse and versatile, no classification can be superimposed on all linguistic material.

For example, from the point of view of dependence on the context, E.A. Pechenikhina highlights linguistic and verbal irony. Linguistic irony requires a minimal context for its implementation, while verbal irony can only be realized when immersed in a certain context. The researcher considers individual-author's or creative irony to be a special kind of speech irony, which has an artistic function and occupies a special place in the ideological-figurative structure of the work.

Another point of view is described by E.V. Martyanov. He divides irony into linguistic and aesthetic. In the case of linguistic irony, a word or expression is used in a meaning directly opposite to its main meaning and with directly opposite connotations. In the case of aesthetic irony, verbal units are attributed not directly opposite meanings, but a whole range of ironically-occasional meanings.

Also, one of the signs of the separation of types of irony is its localization in the statement. The irony contained in the word is called verbal, situational and stylistic. Irony that goes beyond words and phrases is referred to as textual, associative and conceptual. The same classification, only without giving names to the types of irony, is given by A.V. Sergienko. He speaks of two types of irony: irony as a certain stylistic device and a more hidden type of irony, which is characterized by a gradual increment of implicit information.

In the second type of irony, the implementation of figurative meanings occurs gradually; new meanings arise gradually and most often - within the framework of the whole work. This type of irony serves as a means of creating artistic images, revealing the author's intention and worldview in the gradual expansion of the entire text. Let us consider in more detail these types of irony using the example of the classification of O.P. Ermakova and study the irony contained in the word and phrase. In this case, it is important to determine which parts of speech can be used in an ironic sense.

Another classification is offered by I.B. Shatunovsky. He contrasts specific and general irony. In the case of a specific irony, meanings are contrasted with specific propositional, conceptual and illocutionary content. In the case of general irony, an ironic statement is not "ambiguous." It seems to be an ordinary statement, but it carries in itself certain formal signals of irony: ironic intonation, special ironic words. Irony can be divided into communicative and nominative irony. With communicative irony, a communicative unit is ironically interpreted - an utterance or a series of utterances, a piece of text, and with nominative irony, a part of the utterance serving to designate the characteristics of some object of reality, that is, irony is hidden within the utterance.

The first type of irony is the Verbal one. Verbal irony is referred only to spoken words. It happens when a character says one thing, but aims the opposite. For example, a character stepping out into a hurricane and saying, "What a nice weather we're having!" - as we can see the character is defining the situation totally upside down, while in reality he has had an awful weather. Very often verbal irony is confused with sarcasm. Sarcasm is more severe and direct, but the

verbal irony is implicit. At this point I would like to provide a couple of other examples: let's imagine you are walking into a theater and you see almost no audience and you say "it's too crowded!" or you work in a shop and you say to a rude customer "have a nice day!".

The following type is dramatic irony. It deals more with the meaning of the intentions of a character while acting rather than the words. For example, in the play of Othello we can see the dramatic irony when Othello refers to Iago as "honest Iago". Unknown to Othello, Iago is a villain who conducts him to the thought that Desdemona has been unfaithful. For this reason, Othello unfairly kills his wife, believing the whole time in Iago's honesty. Othello calls Iago "honest" and does not know of his deceit.

The next type of irony is the situational one. Situational irony occurs when some circumstances turn out to be the opposite of what is expected or considered to be appropriate. It defies logical cause/effect relationships and justifiable expectations. The Gift of the Magi - in this short story by O. Henry, a husband sells his watch for buying her wife combs for her hair and his wife sells her hair for buying a watch chain. This kind of situation cannot be explained logically and it seems quite "unfair". This sense of being "unfair" or "unfortunate" is the label of situational irony. Because there is no way to explain unfairness, it makes people examine if the world makes sense.

Finally, we have cosmic irony, also called as irony of fate. This type of irony reflects comedic effect like in satire. As an example we can take Jane Austen's famous novel *Pride and Prejudice*. Jane Austen was considered to be the master in using irony and dialogue in his writings. According to

Margaret Atwood (a Canadian poet, novelist, literary critic, essayist, teacher, environmental activist, and inventor) “Her preoccupation with social divisions, and the witty and insightful tone with which she revealed hypocrisy and parodied people contributed heavily to her voice. Austen opens *Pride and Prejudice* with a famous line implying that men are the ones who hunt for a wife; however, she makes it clear throughout the narrative that it is actually the other way around”.

To conclude, irony can be linguistic and literary device in a spoken or written form

where the meaning is implicit or discrepant. The linguistic use of irony is considered sarcasm, while in literature among the most dynamic devices it is mostly used in satire. The definition of irony as a literary device is a situation in which there is a contrast between expectation and reality. For example, the difference between what something appears to mean versus its literal meaning. Irony is associated with both tragedy and humor. There are four major types of irony which are verbal, dramatic, situational and cosmic.

References:

1. Печеникина. Э. Визуальная политическая ирония в современной России. Москва. 2010.
2. Мартянова Э. Й. Много Много ироничных комментариев. Москва. 2007.
3. Сергиенко А.В. Языковые возможности реализации иронии как разновидности импликации в художественных текстах. Саратов, 1995.
4. Эрмакова О.П. Ирония и ее роль жизни языка. Москва. 2005.
5. Шатуновский И.Б. Ирония и ее виды. Логический анализ языка. Языковые механизмы комизма. Москва. 2007.
6. Yaseen K. *The Gift of the Magi Analysis*. London. 2018.
7. Margaret Atwood. *Survival: A Thematic Guide to Canadian Literature*. Canada. 1972. p. 240